

Venous Thromboembolic Disease: Epidemiological-Clinical, Therapeutic, and Evolutionary Aspects at the Reference Hospital of Maradi

La Maladie Thromboembolique Veineuse: Aspects Épidémio-Cliniques, Thérapeutiques et Évolutifs à l'Hôpital de Référence de Maradi

H. Laouan ✉

Faculty of Health Sciences, Dan Dicko Dankoulodo University of Maradi, Niger;
Reference Hospital of Maradi, Niger

S. M. M'baye Salissou

Faculty of Health Sciences, André Salifou University of Zinder, Niger

B. Hassane

Faculty of Health Sciences, Dan Dicko Dankoulodo University of Maradi, Niger;
Reference Hospital of Maradi, Niger

I. Oumarou Amadou

Reference Hospital of Maradi, Niger

N. Hama Aghali

Faculty of Health Sciences, Dan Dicko Dankoulodo University of Maradi, Niger;
Reference Hospital of Maradi, Niger

H. L. Mianroh

Faculty of Health Sciences, Adam Barka University of Abéché, Chad

A. Guéro Tchao

Faculty of Health Sciences, Dan Dicko Dankoulodo University of Maradi, Niger

B. Dodo

Faculty of Health Sciences of Abdou Moumouni University of Niamey, Niger

H. Idrissa

Faculty of Health Sciences of Abdou Moumouni University of Niamey, Niger

M. A. Maliki

Faculty of Health Sciences of Abdou Moumouni University of Niamey, Niger

A. A. Adjougoula Koboy

National Reference University Hospital Center (CHU-RN) of N'Djamena, Chad

H. N. Tsague Kengni

Faculty of Medicine and Biomedical Sciences of the University of Yaoundé 1,
Cameroon

K. B. Abdoul Wahab

Faculty of Medicine and Pharmacy of Mohammed V University, Morocco

L. C. Ngo Yon

Faculty of Medicine and Biomedical Sciences of the University of Yaoundé 1,
Cameroon

M. Bodian

Faculty of Medicine, Pharmacy, and Odonto-Stomatology, Senegal

E. O. Adehossi

Faculty of Health Sciences of Abdou Moumouni University of Niamey, Niger

I. A. Touré

Faculty of Health Sciences of Abdou Moumouni University of Niamey, Niger

More Information

How to cite this article: Laouan H, M'baye Salissou SM, Hassane B, Oumarou Amadou I, Hama Aghali N, Mianroh HL, Guéro Tchao A, Dodo B, Idrissa H, Maliki MA, Adjougoula Koboy AA, Tsague Kengni HN, Abdoul Wahab KB, Ngo Yon LC, Bodian M, Adehossi EO, Touré IA. Venous Thromboembolic Disease: Epidemiological-Clinical, Therapeutic, and Evolutionary Aspects at the Reference Hospital of Maradi. Eur J Med Health Res, 2026;4(1):235-42.

DOI: 10.59324/ejmhr.2026.4(1).33

Keywords:

venous thromboembolic disease, epidemiological and clinical aspects and treatment, Maradi-Niger.

Mots clés:

maladie thrombo-embolique veineuse, aspects épidémio-cliniques et traitement, Maradi-Niger.

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Abstract

Introduction: Venous thromboembolic disease (VTE), including deep vein thrombosis and pulmonary embolism, is a major cause of morbidity and mortality worldwide. Its incidence, estimated at 1 to 2 cases per 1,000 inhabitants per year, increases significantly with age and the presence of comorbidities. **Materials and Methods:** This was a descriptive cross-sectional study with retrospective data collection over a period of 3 years and 3 months from January 1, 2022, to March 31, 2025, in the cardio-neurology department of the Maradi Reference Hospital. Data were collected on a pre-established survey form from patients' medical records and the hospitalization registry. The variables collected included sociodemographic data, VTE risk factors, clinical data, and evolutionary aspects. Data analysis was performed using Epi Info 7.2.5.0 software. **Results:** We collected 32 cases of VTE among 428 hospitalized patients, representing a hospital prevalence of 7.47%. The average age of patients was 50.59 ± 14.65 , ranging from 23 to 80 years old. The predominant risk factors were prolonged bed rest in 53.13% of cases and acute infection in 40.63% of cases. The average length of hospital stay was 9.28 days, with extremes of 3 and 36 days. Pain and unilateral limb edema were the most common reasons for consultation, accounting for 65.62% and 62.50% of DVT cases, respectively. For PE, dyspnea and tachycardia were the most common clinical signs, followed by desaturation in 100% and 72.73% of cases, respectively. DOACs were the most commonly used drugs (84.37% of cases) and 72.73% of patients hospitalized for DVT had received elastic compression. The in-hospital outcome was favorable in 87.50% of cases. **Conclusion:** Venous thromboembolic disease is a reality in our clinical setting. Its management mainly involves direct oral anticoagulants.

Résumé

Introduction : La maladie thromboembolique veineuse (MTEV), comprenant la thrombose veineuse profonde et l'embolie pulmonaire, représente une cause majeure de morbidité et de mortalité à l'échelle mondiale. Son incidence, estimée à 1 à 2 cas pour 1 000 habitants par an, augmente significativement avec l'âge et la présence de comorbidités. **Matériels et Méthode :** Il s'agissait d'une étude transversale descriptive à collecte rétrospective sur une période de 3 ans 3 mois allant du 1er janvier 2022 au 31 mars 2025 dans le service de cardio-neurologie de l'Hôpital de Référence de Maradi. Les données ont été collectées sur une fiche d'enquête préétablie à partir des dossiers médicaux des patients et le registre d'hospitalisation. Les variables collectées avaient porté sur les données socio-démographiques, les facteurs de risque de MTEV, les données cliniques et les aspects évolutifs. L'analyse des données était faite avec le Logiciel épi info 7.2.5.0. **Résultats :** Nous avons collecté 32 cas de MTEV sur 428 patients hospitalisés soit une prévalence hospitalière de 7,47%. L'âge moyen des patients était de $50,59 \text{ ans} \pm 14,65$ avec des extrêmes de 23 et 80 ans. Les facteurs de risque prédominants étaient respectivement l'alitement prolongé dans 53,13 % et l'infection aiguë dans 40,63%. La durée moyenne d'hospitalisation était de 9,28 jours avec des extrêmes de 3 et 36 jours. La douleur et l'œdème unilatéral du membre étaient les motifs de consultation les plus fréquents avec respectivement 65,62% et 62,50% pour la TVP. Pour l'EP la dyspnée et la tachycardie étaient les signes cliniques les plus fréquents suivi de la désaturation dans respectivement 100 % et 72,73% des cas. Les AOD étaient les molécules les plus utilisées (84,37% de cas) et 72,73% des patients hospitalisés pour TVP avaient bénéficié d'une contention élastique [Tableau V]. L'évolution intrahospitalière était favorable dans 87,50 % des cas. **Conclusion :** La maladie thrombo-embolique veineuse est une réalité dans notre contexte clinique. Sa prise en charge fait surtout appel aux anticoagulants oraux directs.

Introduction

Venous thromboembolism (VTE) is an anatomico-clinical entity characterized by a more or less complete obstruction of a vein by a thrombus resulting from localized intravascular coagulation. The most common manifestations are deep vein thrombosis, which generally occurs in the lower limbs, and pulmonary embolism. It is the third most frequent cardiovascular disease after myocardial infarction and stroke. It represents a major cause of mortality and morbidity. Its incidence ranges from 100 to 200 cases per 100,000 people per year. However, this incidence shows a wide variation from one country to another. In the United States, it is estimated that there are about 600,000 annual cases of VTE, with 30% resulting in death.

In Europe, the estimated average annual incidence rate of overall VTE ranges from 104 to 183 per 100,000 people/year, and the estimated incidence of DVT was 148 per 100,000 people/year. Similarly, the estimated incidence of PE was 95 cases per 100,000 people/year. This pathology poses a diagnostic problem even in developed countries, where autopsied cases are more frequent than diagnosed cases, with 70% of deaths from pulmonary embolism not diagnosed during the patient's lifetime, and therapeutic challenges, especially in our countries, due to the cost of care. In sub-Saharan Africa, studies conducted on the MTEV have shown: In Timbuktu (Mali), the incidence of DVT was estimated at 1.2% in 2023, while in Côte d'Ivoire it reached 5.4% in 2019. A study conducted in 2024 at the Hospital of Peace in Ziguinchor reported a prevalence

of 0.87%, including 0.69% for DVT and 0.18% for PE. In N'Djamena, an incidence of 7.54% was noted in 2024. In Niger, hospital studies showed a prevalence of 3.9% in 2021 at the National Hospital of Niamey, with 2.78% for DVT, 0.55% for PE, and 0.55% for the association of DVT+PE. The prevalence of DVT was estimated at 9.4% in 2018 in two hospital centers in Niamey, and then at 8.41% in 2022 in the cardiology department of the National Hospital of Niamey (HNN).

In Maradi region, we did not find any studies on this pathology, hence the necessity of this work to fill the existing gap.

Materials and Methods

This is a descriptive cross-sectional study with retrospective data collection over a period of 3 years and 3 months, from January 1, 2022, to March 31, 2025, in the cardiology-neurology department of the Reference Hospital of Maradi (HRM).

Inclusion Criteria

We included in our study all hospitalized patients for deep vein thrombosis or pulmonary embolism whose diagnosis was confirmed.

Exclusion criteria: Patients with unusable records.

Data Collection

Data were collected on a pre-established survey form from the patients' medical records and the hospitalization register.

Studied variables: We collected sociodemographic data (age, sex, profession, origin, marital status), risk factors for VTE, clinical data (reason for consultation, duration of symptoms before admission, clinical entity, clinical signs of DVT and PE, Wells Score), the molecules used, and evolutionary aspects (Improved, complications, length of stay, death).

Data Entry and Analysis

Data entry was performed using ODK Collect v2024.1.2. The Epi Info 7.2.5.0 software allowed us to analyze the data.

Bivariate analysis aimed to study the associations between clinical and therapeutic factors and the occurrence of complications or clinical improvement. Qualitative variables were grouped into two modalities to avoid low counts in the cells and allow the use of Fisher's exact test, while respecting clinical relevance.

Results

During the study period, we collected 32 cases of VTE out of 428 hospitalized patients in cardiology at HRM from January 1, 2022, to March 31, 2025, resulting in a hospital prevalence of 7.47%.

The average age of the patients was 50.59 years ± 14.65 with extremes of 23 and 80 years. The female sex was the most represented with a rate of 62.50% and a sex ratio (M/F) of 0.6. Housewives were the most represented with a percentage of 43.75%. The majority of patients came from Maradi city at 56.25%. Married subjects represented 81.25%.

The predominant risk factors were prolonged bed rest at 53.13% and acute infection at 40.63% [Table 1]. The average length of hospitalization was 9.28 days with extremes of 3 and 36 days.

Table 1: Distribution of Patients According to Acquired Risk Factors

Risk factors	Number (nb)	Percentage (%)
History of venous thrombosis	1	3,13
Alcohol	1	3,13
Overweight	4	12,50
Tumor	4	12,50
Prolonged bed rest	17	53,13
Recent surgery	4	12,50
Postpartum	2	6,25
Heart failure decompensation	1	3,13
Oral contraception	9	28,13
Acute infection	13	40,63
Age over 75 years	2	6,25
Tobacco	2	6,25
Stroke	7	21,88
Diabetes	3	9,37

Figure 1: Distribution of Patients According to Clinical Entity

Clinical Signs

Pain and unilateral edema of the limb were the most frequent reasons for consultation with 65.62% and 62.50% for DVT, respectively. More than half of the patients were hospitalized within the first week following the onset of symptoms, accounting for 65.63% [Table 2]. The average duration of symptoms before hospitalization was 7.43 days ± 4.44 with extremes of 1 to 28 days.

For PE, dyspnea and tachycardia were the most frequent clinical signs, followed by desaturation in 100% and 72.73% of cases, respectively [Table 3]. The clinical probability of Wells was intermediate in 43.75%. Patients who presented with isolated venous thrombosis were predominant with a rate of 65.63% (21 cases) [Figure 1]. The popliteal-femoral site was the most represented for DVT at 45.44%.

Table 2: Distribution of Patients According to the Duration of Symptoms before Admission

Onset of symptoms (days)	Number (nb)	Percentage (%)
≤ 7 days	21	65,63
More than 7 days	11	34,37
Total	32	100,00

Table 3: Distribution of Patients According to Clinical Signs of PE at Admission

Clinical signs of pulmonary embolism	Number (nb)	Percentage (%)
Dyspnea	11	100,00
Hemoptysis	3	27,27
Tachycardia	11	100,00
Desaturation	8	72,73
Others	5	45,45

Table 4: Distribution of Patients According to Clinical Signs of Deep Vein Thrombosis

Clinical signs of deep vein thrombosis	Number (nb)	Percentage (%)
Fever	8	38,10
Thigh/leg pain	20	95,24
Unilateral edema	20	95,24
Decreased calf tenderness	15	71,43
Positive Homan's sign	13	61,90
Local warmth	13	61,90
Others	3	14,29

Treatment and Evolution

Direct oral anticoagulants (DOACs) were the most commonly used agents (84.37% of cases) and 72.73% of patients hospitalized for DVT had received elastic compression [Table 5].

The in-hospital evolution was favorable in 87.50% of cases [Table 6].

The average length of hospitalization was 9.28 days and 56.25% of patients had a length of stay greater than 7 days.

Table 5: Distribution of Patients According to the Therapeutic Scheme Used

Therapeutic scheme	Number of cases	Percentage (%)
LMWH then DOAC	27	84,37
LMWH + VKAs	5	15,63
Total	32	100 ,00

Table 6: Distribution of Patients According to Evolving Modalities

Evolving modalities	Number (nb)	Percentage (%)
Complications	3	9,37
Death	1	3,13
Improved	28	87,50
Total	32	100,00

Bivariate Analysis

The bivariate analysis did not detect an association between the explored variables.

Table 7: Duration of Symptoms at Admission and Complications

Duration of symptoms at admission (days)	Complications		Total
	No	Yes	
≤ 7	19 (90.48%)	2 (9.52%)	21 (100.00%)
> 7	9 (81.82%)	2 (18.18%)	11 (100.00%)
Total	28 (87.50%)	4 (12.50%)	32 (100.00%)

Note: P=0.48; Fisher's exact test=0.59

Table 8: Tobacco and Complications

Tobacco	Complications		Total
	Yes	No	
Yes	0 (0%)	2 (100%)	2 (100%)
No	4 (13.33%)	26 (86.67%)	30 (100%)
Total	4 (12.50%)	28 (87.50%)	32 (100%)

Note: P=0.76

Table 10: Consultation Delay and Length of Stay

Duration of symptoms before admission (days)	Length of stay (days)		Total
	≤ 7	> 7	
≤ 7	8 (38.10%)	13 (61.86%)	21 (100.00%)
> 7	6 (54.55%)	5 (45.45%)	11 (100.00%)

Total	14 (43.75%)	18 (56.25%)	32 (100.00%)
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Note: P=0.60; Fisher's exact test=0.40

Ethical Consideration

Research authorization was obtained in advance from the authorities of the Reference Hospital of Maradi. Anonymity and confidentiality of the data are preserved.

Limitations of the Study

Insufficient maintenance of patient records.

Discussion

During the period of our study, 32 patients were hospitalized for VTE, resulting in a hospital prevalence of 7.47%, including 68.75% (n=22) of deep vein thrombosis; 34.37% (n=11) of pulmonary embolism, and one case of combined DVT+PE.

These results are similar to those reported by Abdel-Madjid et al. [10] in Chad in 2024, who observed an overall prevalence of VTE of 7.54%, and are close to those of

This difference in frequency may be due to the differences in collection durations and the number of study sites.

It could also be related to methodological differences used for diagnosis. The diagnostic methods vary from one region to another due to a lack of technical resources, and access to care was limited until 2024, which underestimates the prevalence of this condition in our context.

In our series, the year 2024 was the most represented with 14 cases, accounting for 43.75%.

This predominance could be explained by the reduction in healthcare costs in 2024 by the state, which facilitated access to care in public facilities.

Socio-Demographic Data

The average age of patients included in our study was 50.59 ± 14.65 years, with extremes ranging from 23 to 80 years. The most represented age group was that of 40 to 60 years, with a rate of 53.13%.

These results are consistent with those reported by several authors. Indeed, Abdel-Madjid et al. [10] observed a predominant age group of 40 to 60 years with an average age of 47.8 ± 14.5 years. Similarly, Diagne in Ziguinchor, Senegal [9] in 2024 reported an average age of 51.27 ± 18 years, with the 40 to 60 age group also being the most represented.

Furthermore, Diarra [14] in Bamako in 2023 found an average age of 50.68 ± 16.32 years with extreme values from 21 to 83 years, while Camara Y et al. [15] at the CHU of Kati in 2022 reported an average age of 52.9 ± 16.4 years with a predominant age group of 47 to 59 years and similar extremes ranging from 21 to 83 years. These data suggest that the age of onset of venous thromboembolism (VTE) is relatively lower in African subjects than that reported in Western literature. This

predominance could be explained by the high proportion of young people in the African population. Moreover, it is well established in the literature that there is a positive correlation between age and the frequency of VTE, with the prevalence of the disease increasing exponentially with advancing age.

The female sex was the most represented in our series, with a proportion of 62.50%, resulting in a sex ratio (M/F) of 0.6.

These results are consistent with those reported by several authors. Indeed, Silvy et al. [16] in Yaoundé in 2022 observed a female predominance of 65.1%, with a sex ratio of 0.5, while Diarra [14] in Bamako in 2023 found a female predominance of 58.8%. This same trend was also observed in Nigerien studies by Touré et al. [11] in 2021 and Idrissa et al. [13] in Niamey in 2022, which reported 58% and 60% of women, respectively.

The female predominance observed in our study could be attributed to specific hormonal factors related to the female sex, including the influence of oral contraceptives, pregnancy, and the postpartum period. It could also be reinforced by the demographic structure of the Nigerien population, which is predominantly female, as well as by the greater sedentariness often observed in this gender.

Housewives constituted the most represented group, with a proportion of 43.75%. A similar trend was observed by Melingui [17] in Bamako in 2020, Abdel-Madjid et al. [10] in Chad, and Idrissa et al. [13] in Niamey in 2022, reporting 48%, 44.4%, 34.7%, and 36%, respectively.

This predominance could be explained by the fact that housewives represent the most frequent socio-professional category in these countries, as well as by the strong correlation between VTE and sedentariness, particularly observed among homemakers.

In our sample, married subjects represented 81.25%. This result is identical to that of Idrissa et al. [13] in Niamey in 2022 and higher than that of Diagne in Ziguinchor, Senegal [9] in 2024, who found 82% and 56.86%, respectively.

This predominance could be explained by the religious nature of the adult population in Niger.

The most observed risk factors were prolonged bed rest in 53.13% of patients, followed by acute infection in 40.63%. These results corroborate those of our predecessors, notably those of Abdel-madjid et al. [10] in Chad in 2024; Silvy et al. [16] in Yaoundé in 2022, who reported 52.4% and 51.1% of cases of prolonged bed rest, respectively.

These results indicate that prolonged bed rest is a major risk factor for VTE. Indeed, all situations leading to an alteration of the muscle pump dependent on walking are associated with an increased risk of VTE occurrence. In the AT-AGE study, it was determined that immobilization (hospitalization, surgery, fracture,

plaster, minor limb trauma, and transient immobility) is associated with an increased venous thrombotic risk [18].

Clinical Aspects

According to our anamnesis data, the most frequent reason for consultation was unilateral painful swelling of the limb, found in 65.62% of patients. These results are comparable to those reported by Abdel-madjid et al. [10], who noted a painful swollen leg in 62.5% of patients, but remain higher than those of Touré et al. [11], who found 46.4% of painful edema of the lower limb.

This variation could be explained by the non-specific nature of these signs.

More than half of the patients were hospitalized in the first week following the onset of symptoms, at 65.63%. These results are close to those of Touré et al. [11] in 2021 in Niamey and Walbane [19], who each noted 52.90%. This could be explained by the symptomatic nature of VTE, which becomes increasingly unbearable, as well as the reality of our population consulting late.

Data for DVT

Clinical Signs

In our series, the most frequently observed physical signs in deep vein thrombosis were pain in the thigh/calf and unilateral limb swelling, noted in 95.24% each, followed by a decrease in calf tenderness in 71.43%, then an increase in local warmth and a positive Homan's sign in 61.90% each. Finally, fever was noted in 38.10%.

These signs are found in most studies conducted on DVT, but with percentages that differ from one study to another.

The study by Njonnou et al. [20] reported a predominance of limb pain (93%), followed by a decrease in calf tenderness (86%) and limb swelling in 82.4%.

Diagne [9] in Senegal in 2024 in his series found limb swelling in 100%, limb pain (86.42%), an increase in local warmth (62.96%), a positive Homan's sign in 43.21%, and a decrease in calf tenderness (41.98%).

This variation in percentages could be explained by the low sensitivity and specificity of the clinical signs of deep vein thrombosis. Indeed, these signs are unreliable; their sensitivity is limited, especially in asymptomatic forms where they may be absent, and their specificity is reduced since they can also occur in other pathologies. Each sign may present in isolation, but their association increases their diagnostic value [21]. Thus, clinical prediction scores have been developed to estimate the clinical probability of this condition.

Topographically, the venous thromboses in our study were located in the lower limbs in 95.45% and were primarily situated on the right side in 54.55%.

Walbane [20] in his series reported a localization of 98.25% in the lower limbs, of which 57.89% was on the left.

Coulibaly S et al. [22] also reported a localization of 94.12% in the lower limbs, of which 55.90% was on the left.

Thus, the predominance of DVT in the left lower limb would be due to venous compression by May-Thurner syndrome: This syndrome occurs when an artery (right iliac artery) compresses the left iliac vein against the spine. This increases the risk of DVT in the left leg as the vein is partially obstructed, slowing blood flow and increasing the risk of clot formation [23].

The predominance of DVT localization in the right lower limb in our study is probably due to the small size of our sample.

In our study, more than half (59.10%) of the patients had presented a high clinical probability. Our results are in agreement with those of Diarra [14] in Bamako in 2025; Mariko et al. [7] in Timbuktu and Camara Y et al. [99] at the CHU of Kati in 2022, who reported a predominance of high Wells scores in 93.3%; 87.5% and 91.3%, respectively.

Data for Pulmonary Embolism

In our series, dyspnea and tachycardia were the most frequent clinical signs, followed by desaturation in 100% and 72.73% of cases, respectively.

Hemoptysis was found in 27.27% of patients.

These same symptoms were reported by most authors in the literature, but at differing percentages.

Silvy et al. [16] in Yaoundé in 2022 noted a predominance of dyspnea in 100%, followed by tachycardia in 60.5%, chest pain in 32.6%, and hemoptysis in 16.3%, while Njonnou et al. [20] reported a higher frequency for dyspnea (100%), followed by tachypnea (87.2%) and chest pain (70.2%).

As for Ly [24], he found symptoms such as dyspnea (100%), tachycardia (100%), cough (90%), chest pain (70%), and hemoptysis (50%).

This great variability in the results of different studies could be explained by the nonspecific nature of these symptoms, which are found in most cardio-respiratory pathologies. Clinical evaluation of patients suspected of pulmonary embolism is crucial as it allows for the implicit determination or, with the help of prediction scores, the clinical probability of pulmonary embolism, an essential step in diagnostic strategies [25].

In our series, according to the Wells score, an intermediate clinical probability was found in the majority of patients, at 72.73%. This predominance of intermediate probability was also reported by Touré et al. [11] in Niamey and Diagne [9] in Senegal in 2024, who found frequencies of 70% and 66.67%, respectively.

Aspects of Treatment

In our series, the most commonly used therapeutic regimen was LMWH followed by a switch to DOACs in 56.25%, followed by DOACs alone in 28.13%, then a LMWH-VKA overlap in 15.62%, and no cases of thrombolysis were recorded.

The data found in our study are similar to those of Dakouo et al. [26] at the CH of Montluçon, which reported the use of DOACs in 77.7% and an LMWH-VKA overlap in 5.6% of patients. Silvy et al. [16] in Yaoundé in 2022 noted a predominance of the use of DOACs (81%) and an LMWH-VKA overlap in 14.4% of patients. The choice of prescribers to use DOACs could be explained by their availability, accessibility, and especially their easier handling compared to VKAs.

Regarding adjunctive treatment, 72.73% of patients hospitalized for DVT had benefited from elastic compression.

Our results corroborate those of Diagne [9] in Senegal in 2024 and Mariko et al. [7] in Mali, who reported 66.6% and 96.30%, respectively. This could be explained by its role in preventing post-thrombotic disease, its analgesic effect, and the reduction of thrombotic progression.

In our series, the intrahospital evolution was generally favorable under anticoagulation in 84.37% of cases. However, we noted some complications, including recurrent DVT, DVT complicated by PE, one case of pulmonary infarction, and one death. These results are consistent with those reported by Diagne [9] and Ly [24], who observed a favorable intrahospital evolution in 84.31%, 90%, and 81.60% of cases, respectively.

These results could be attributed to diligent management with respect to decision-making hierarchies (diagnostic algorithm and care protocol) and an early start of treatment as soon as diagnostic suspicion arises, sometimes even before paraclinical confirmation.

In our series, the average length of hospitalization was 9.28 days, with extremes of 3 and 36 days. This average length of hospitalization is longer than that found by Syna [16], who noted an average length of hospitalization of 7.36 ± 4.5 days.

This difference in the length of hospitalization may be explained by the differing profiles of patients from one series to another, and in our series, patients presenting with VTE on a background of stroke had a longer length of stay.

Conclusion

Venous thromboembolic disease is a common condition at the Reference Hospital of Mardi. The in-hospital evolution was favorable in our series in 87.50% of cases. A prospective study on a larger sample will allow for a better specification of the epidemiological, clinical, and therapeutic characteristics of this condition.

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